

Table 1: Effect of specific diet regimes and lifestyle interventions on metabolic outcomes (glycemia, lipidemia, cardiovascular disease factors) in individuals at high risk for developing or with Type 2 diabetes

Study	Health status Age (years) BMI (kg/m ²)	Duration and design of dietary intervention	Sample size	Description of groups	Dietary intervention	Selected clinical outcomes
<p>• Effect of lifestyle interventions on glycemia and other major metabolic outcomes in diabetic individuals</p>						
Johansen, <i>et al.</i> , 2017 [75]	T2D 54.6 25-40	12 months Randomized, assessor-blinded, single-center study	98	Lifestyle group (LG) Standard care (SC)	LG: 5-6 weekly aerobic sessions of 30-60mins, with 2-3 sessions of resistance training and an individual dietary plan with 45%-60% CHO, 15%-20% PRO, and 20%-35% FAT (<7% saturated fat) SC: medical counseling, lifestyle advice	HbA1c (mmol/l) 6.65% - 6.34% in LG 6.74% - 6.66% in SC Reduction in Glu-lowering medications -73.5% in LG -26.4% in SC
Linmans, <i>et al.</i> , 2011 [90]	IGT or T2D 62.9±11.8 30.4±4.9	1 year Randomized trial	2818	Intervention group (IG) Control group (CG)	IG: with lifestyle coaches supervising the program, >30mins exercise for >5 days/wk CG: usual care according to a diabetes management program	IG group: HbA1c (mmol/l) -0.12% Fasting Glu (mmol/l) -0.17 NS changes in the CG
Chee, <i>et al.</i> , 2017 [91]	Overweight/obese, T2D, and HbA1c 7%–11% 30–65 >23	6 months Randomized controlled clinical trial	230	Usual care (UC) Trans-cultural diabetes nutrition algorithm-conventional counseling (tDNA-CC)	UC: clinical care according to Malaysian Clinical Practice Guidelines for T2D (2009) and low-calorie diet (1200 or 1500 kcal/day) tDNA-CC low-calorie meal plan (1200 or 1500 kcal/day) and a physical activity prescription for >150 min/wk with conventional counseling	tDNA-MI BW (kg) -6.9±1.3 in tDNA-MI -5.3±1.2 in tDNA-CC -0.8±0.5 NS in UC A1c (mmol/l) -1.1±0.1% in tDNA-MI -0.5±0.1% in tDNA-CC

				Trans-cultural diabetes nutrition algorithm-motivational interviewing (tDNA-MI)	tDNA-MI low-calorie meal plan (1200 or 1500 kcal/day) and a physical activity prescription for >150 min/wk with motivational interviewing	-0.2±0.1%, NS in UC Fasting plasma Glu (mmol/L) -1.1±0.3 in tDNA-MI -0.6±0.3, NS in tDNA-CC 0.1±0.3, NS in UC Systolic BP (mm Hg) -9±2 in tDNA-MI -9±2 in tDNA-CC -1±2, NS in UC
Wing <i>et al.</i> , 2010 [92]	T2D 58.6±6.8 35.9±6.0	11 Years Randomized, controlled trial	5145	Intensive lifestyle intervention (ILI) Diabetes support and education (DSE, control group)	ILI: usual medical care combined with an intensive 4-year program designed to increase physical activity and reduce initial weight by 7% or more. DSE: usual medical care, provided by their own primary care physicians, plus three group educational sessions per year for the first 4 years	<u>After 4 years:</u> BW (kg) -6.15% in ILI vs -0.88% in DSE HbA1c (mmol/l) -0.36% in ILI vs 0.09% in DSE systolic BP (mmHg) -5.33 in ILI vs -2.97 in DSE diastolic BP (mmHg) -2.92 in ILI vs -2.48 in DSE HDL (mg/dl) 3.67 in ILI vs 1.97 in DSE

						TG (mg/dl) -25.56 in ILI vs -19.75 in DSE
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• **Effect of lifestyle interventions on glycemia and other major metabolic outcomes in individuals with impaired glucose tolerance or at high risk for T2D**

Diabetes Prevention Program Research Group 2015 [62]	At high risk for T2D 50.6±10.7 34.0±6.7	15 years Randomized controlled clinical trial	3234	Intensive lifestyle intervention (ILS) Metformin (MET) Placebo (PLBO)	ILS: low calorie and low lipid diet, plus 150min physical activity per week MET: 850mg x2/day PLBO: x2/day	ILS: ↓18% diabetes incidence rate MET: ↓27% diabetes incidence rate ILS: ↓8.7% aggregate microvascular prevalence in women
O'Brien, <i>et al.</i> , 2017 [63]	IGT 45.1±12.5 33.3±6.5	12 months Randomized, pilot study	96	Intensive lifestyle intervention (ILI) Metformin (MET) Standard care (SC)	ILI: weight loss (5%–7% of initial body weight) by improving dietary patterns (decreasing fat and calories) and promoting moderate physical activity (≥150 min per week) MET: 850mg of metformin x2/day SC: medical care and educational materials on diabetes prevention from the National Diabetes Education Program	BW (kg) -4.0 in ILI -0.9 in MET +0.8 in SC Waist circumference (cm) -4 in ILI -1.8 in MET -0.2 in SC
Lindström, <i>et al.</i> , 2006 [65]	Overweight with IGT 55 31.1	7 years Randomized controlled trial	522	Intervention group (IG) Control group (CG)	IG: <30% FAT, < 10% saturated FAT, >15g per 1000kcal Fibers, and moderately intense physical activity 30min per day or more	Incidence of type 2 diabetes 4.3 per 100 person-years (IG) vs. 7.4 per100 person-years (CG)

					CG: general health information at baseline without specific individualized advice	↓43% relative risk in IG
Ujvari, <i>et al.</i> , 2014 [70]	18–40 PCOS and BMI >27 kg/m ² Healthy overweight/o bese women (OB-C) PCOS and normal weight BMI 18.5–25 Healthy women and BMI 18.5–25	3 months Randomized trial	49	Overweight/ obese women with PCOS (OB-PCOS) Overweight/obe se controls (OB- C) Normal-weight PCOS (NW- PCOS) Healthy normal- weight controls (NW-C)	OB: PCOS-dietary restriction diet high in PRO and low in CHO (40% CHO, 30% FAT, and 30% PRO), and activity for 45 min 2-3 times/wk	BW (kg) -4.7 Ins (uU/ml) -11.9 Relative mRNA levels IRS1 +0.28 GLUT1 +0.06
Slentz, <i>et al.</i> , 2016 [76]	Overweight /obese) 45–75 25–35	6 months Randomized, parallel clinical trial	150	High amount/moderat e intensity physical activity (1) High amount/vigorou s intensity physical activity (2)	(1) High amount -(67 KKW) /moderate intensity: equivalent of expending 67 KKW (~22.3 km (13.8 miles) per week) with moderate-intensity exercise (2) High amount (67KKW)/vigorous intensity- equivalent to group 2, but with vigorous-intensity exercise (75% peak $\dot{V}O_{2reserve}$) (3) Low amount- (42 kJ kg body weight ⁻¹ week ⁻¹ (KKW)//moderate intensity: equivalent of expending 42	BW (kg) -1.94 in (1) -1.67 in (2) NS in (3) -6.44 in (4) Fat mass (kg) -2.2 in (1) -2.3 in (2) NS in (3) -6.0 in (4) AUC _{Glu} (mmol/l×120 min)

				<p>Low amount/moderate intensity physical activity (3)</p> <p>Lifestyle intervention with low amount/moderate intensity physical activity + diet (4)</p>	<p>KKW (e.g., walking ~16 km (8.6 miles) per week) with moderate-intensity (50% peak $\dot{V}O_{2\text{reserve}}$) exercise</p> <p>(4) diet + 42 KKW moderate intensity-same as group 1 but with diet and weight loss (7%) to mimic the first 6 months of the DPP.</p>	<p>-73 in (1)</p> <p>-22 in (2)</p> <p>NS in (3)</p> <p>-96 in (4)</p> <p>AUC_{Ins} (pmol/l×2h)</p> <p>-264 in (1)</p> <p>-246 in (2)</p> <p>-166 in (3)</p> <p>-348 in (4)</p>
Mensink, <i>et al.</i> , 2003 [78]	<p>IGT</p> <p>55.6±0.9</p> <p>29.8±0.5</p>	<p>2 years</p> <p>Randomized trial</p>	<p>114</p>	<p>lifestyle intervention group (INT)</p> <p>Control group (CON)</p>	<p>INT</p> <p><35% FAT,</p> <p><10% saturated FAT,</p> <p>>3g/MJ fibers,</p> <p>physical activity for at least 1 h/wk</p> <p>CON</p> <p>usual care according to a diabetes management program</p>	<p><u>INT:</u></p> <p>BW (kg)</p> <p>-2.4±0.7</p> <p>Body fat (%)</p> <p>-1.0±0.3</p> <p>Waist (cm)</p> <p>-1.9±0.7</p> <p>Fast Glu (Mm)</p> <p>+0,2±0.1</p> <p>2h Glu (Mm)</p> <p>-0,6±0.3</p> <p>Fast Ins (Mm/L)</p> <p>-1,8±1.7</p> <p>HOMA</p> <p>-0.5±0.5</p>

Roumen, <i>et al.</i> , 2008 [94]	IGT 54.2±5.8 29.6±3.8	3 years Randomized controlled lifestyle intervention	106	Intervention group (INT) Control group (CON)	INT: Dietary recommendations as per Dutch guidelines for a healthy diet, and physical activity of at least 30min a day for at least 5 days a week CON: usual care according to a diabetes management program	<u>After 3 years in INT:</u> BW (kg) -1.08±4.30 vs +0.16±4.91 CON BMI (kg/m ²) -0.36±1.47 BFM (Kg) -1.16±3.80 Fasting Glu (Mm) +0,2±0.1 2h Glu (Mm) -0.05±2.02 Fasting Ins (Mu/L) -1.17 HOMA -0.19
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Abbreviations: IGT: impaired glucose tolerance; T2D: type 2 diabetes; Glu: Glucose; Ins: Insulin; AUC: Area Under the Curve; CHO: carbohydrates; PRO: proteins; FAT: fats; NS: no statistical significant difference; BW: body weight; HbA1c: glycated hemoglobin A1c; BP: blood pressure; HDL: high density lipoprotein cholesterol; TG: triglycerides; BMI: body mass index; BFM: body fat mass